

agro BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report

Responsible Partner: MTU

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“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report Ireland

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of MTU for the organisation and validation of the **Let's Meet Culinary Event, Feirmeoir, Bia agus Chef! - Farmer, Food and Chef event** in Ireland on the **4th of March 2023**. This event is one of the four "Let's meet!" event concepts designed as part of agroBRIDGES Task 3.4 for the local promotion of Short Food Supply Chains, locally produced food and involved market actors, namely (i) Producer Events, (ii) Culinary Events, (iii) Celebrate local heroes / SFSCs, and (iv) Open Days. The organisation, planning and implementation of the event was performed using the guidelines and templates designed by FBCD for each event concept to enable actors in the agri-food sector in replicating the events in their local agri-food ecosystems.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and MTU, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the "Let's meet!" tool. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the Let's Meet Culinary Event (Feirmeoir, Bia agus Chef! - Farmer, Food and Chef!) event in Ireland.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the "Let's meet!" guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the "Let's meet!" tool.

2. “Let’s meet!” event organisation details

2.1 Concept selection and definition of activities (programme)

The Culinary event concept was chosen in Ireland and the event was titled: **Férmúir, Bia agus chef! (Farmer, Food and chef!)**. The event took place on the **4th of March 2023 between 13:30 and 15:30 at Airfield Estate in Dublin**. During the event, three professional chefs prepared a dish each highlighting ingredients provided by four agroBRIDGES SFSC MAP producers. The meals were scored by three expert judges as well as by the event guests consisting of 50 members of the public. Event attendees were given an overview of the agroBRIDGES project, which introduced the concept of SFSCs. Producers were interviewed and had display stands on site to display a sample of their produce.

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Short description	Time (local)	Location
Event opening	Arrivals and registration	13:20	The Hive (Airfield Estate)
agroBRIDGES Project Overview	Project overview presentation and explanation of the benefits of short food supply chain, by Jennifer Attard	13:30	The Hive (Airfield Estate)
What goes on at Airfield Estate?	Presentation of history and activities at Airfield Estate	13:40	The Hive (Airfield Estate)
Interview with Drumanilra Organic Farm	Journalist Janine Kennedy interviewed Justina Gavin, a SFSC producer and one of the produce suppliers for the event.	13:50	The Hive (Airfield Estate)
Dish Tasting	Attendees walk to the kitchen to listen to the chefs talk about each dish, while they finish preparing taster plates for each guest. Each guest was provided a small portion of each of the three dishes.	14:05	Inspiration Kitchen (Airfield Estate)
Meet your producers	Attendees walked back to The Hive for tea, coffees and pastries for a short break and the opportunity to chat to the producers of the day at their display stands. During this time, the attendees were given the voting QR code and allowed to score the dishes.	14:50	The Hive (Airfield Estate)

Title of activity	Short description	Time (local)	Location
Interview with Manna Organic Farm	Journalist Janine Kennedy interviewed Thomas and Claire O'Connor, a SFSC producer and shop owner, and one of the produce suppliers for the event.	15:10	The Hive (Airfield Estate)
Judges Scoring and Award Announcement	Three expert judges explained their feedback and comments on each of the three dishes. Organisers added up the scores and announced the winner. The winner was presented with a prize.	15:20	The Hive (Airfield Estate)
Event closing	Jennifer Attard thanked all involved and closed the event.	15:30	The Hive (Airfield Estate)

2.2 Location, Venue/Space selection and arrangements

The event was hosted at Airfield Estate, Dublin. Airfield Estate is Dublin's only working farm, producing dairy, meat protein, eggs and vegetables for use in the on-site restaurant and for sale in Airfields farmer's market. Airfield Estate provides training & education in horticulture, animal husbandry and cooking. Airfield Estate operates as a sustainable food hub in suburban Dublin. The 38-acre estate is in the South Dublin suburb of Dundrum, 15 minutes by tram from the city centre.

The event attendees gathered in The Hive, which is an indoor space at Airfield Estate with presentation facilities, which allowed guests to listen to the project overview and producer interviews. Produce was prepared and cooked in the Inspiration Kitchen on-site in Airfield Estate, by the 3 chefs. The meal scoring and prize giving also took place in The Hive following the tasting. The hive is located 250m walk from the Inspiration kitchen. Airfield Estate also provided tea, coffee and pastries in The Hive. Airfield Estate used their website to create a registration page and bookings were opened 3 weeks before the event.

Figure 1: Airfield House (a) and Airfield Kitchen gardens (b) (photos taken from <https://www.airfield.ie/>)

Figure 2: (a) The Inspiration Kitchen and (b) The Hive (photos by Janine Kennedy and David Barry)

2.3 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Graphic designers	1	Development of promo material	In-house	2
Marketing & Ticket sales	1	Posting material	In-house	3
Catering	2	Tea & Coffee for guests	External	
Producers	4	Supply produce	External	$1.0 * 4 = 4$
Chefs	3	Preparing food	External	$1.5 * 3 = 4.5$
Ticketing	1	Accepting bookings	External	0.5
Event Judges	3	Judging dishes & giving interviews	External	$0.5 * 3 = 1.5$
Administration	2	Administration	In-house & External	8
Journalist/moderator	1	Interviewing producers & chefs	External	2

2.4 Event material

All provided templates were used except for the participants list since the provision of informed consent for the processing of personal data (as per the GDPR) was required on the day.

Figure 3: (a) social media flyer, (b) detailed social media poster and (c) event programme.

(a) Social media flyer for 'Feirmeoir, Bia agus Chef!' featuring event details, logos, and a chef's hands.

(b) Detailed social media poster for 'Feirmeoir, Bia agus Chef!' featuring event details, a description of the event, and a 'REGISTER HERE' button.

(c) Event programme for 'Feirmeoir, Bia agus Chef!' featuring a vertical 'PROGRAMME' title and a list of activities with times.

Feirmeoir, Bia agus Chef!
Connecting local food producers and chefs with consumers and customers
4th March 2023
1:30 – 3:30pm
Airfield Estate, Overend Way, Dundrum, Dublin 14, Ireland D14 EE77
Learn more on www.agroBRIDGES.eu and follow us on [Twitter](#) [LinkedIn](#)

Feirmeoir, Bia agus Chef!
4th March 2023
1:30 – 3:30pm
Experience fresh Irish food, as prepared by brilliant Irish chefs!
We've invited three highly talented chefs to compete in preparing a taster dish each, made from seasonal local produce from selected small Irish farms. Throughout the event, journalist Janine Kennedy will be interviewing the local producers who are providing fresh ingredients for the dishes.
Guests will be able to watch the chefs as they prepare their local food creations. Each guest will then be served a taster dish from every chef. You, along with three expert judges, will be scoring the dishes to decide on the winning Irish dish!
Reserve your free ticket now to taste Irish food prepared by its experts, and for the opportunity to chat to your local producers and chefs.
Airfield Estate, Overend Way, Dundrum, Dublin 14, Ireland D14 EE77
[REGISTER HERE](#)
Learn more on www.agrobridges.eu and follow us on [Twitter](#) [LinkedIn](#)

Feirmeoir, Bia agus Chef!
4th March 2023
PROGRAMME
13:20-13:30 Arrivals and Registration
13:30-13:40 AgroBRIDGES Project Overview
13:40-13:50 What goes on at Airfield Estate?
13:50-14:05 Interview with Drumanilla Organic Farm
14:05-14:30 Dish Tasting & Meet your Producers
14:30-14:45 Interview with Manna Organic Farm
14:45-15:10 Dish Tasting & Meet your Producers
15:10-15:20 Judges Scoring
15:20-15:30 Award Announcement
Airfield Estate, Overend Way, Dundrum, Dublin 14, Ireland D14 EE77
Learn more on www.agrobridges.eu and follow us on [Twitter](#) [LinkedIn](#)

The below template was sent to all producers, chefs and judges four weeks prior to the event. This facilitated the preparation of a press bio for each actor and permission to share information. The press bio pack information was used for the creation of the online marketing posts and circulated to press journalists to provide background information for promotion prior to the event and articles following the event. A new chef or producer bio was circulated every 3 to 4 days in the 4 weeks leading up to the event.

Figure 4: (a) Press bio template for event stakeholders and (b) example of final social media bio

(a)

(b)

2.5 Engagement of contributors and collaborators

Airfield Estate was selected as the venue for the event for several key reasons:

- They are agroBRIDGES project MAP members,
- They are producers of both meat protein & vegetables,
- They have adequate facilities for food preparation, cooking & serving,
- They have a seating and presentation area,
- They have on-site catering facilities to supply tea/coffee,
- They have experience in hosting events of this nature such as conferences, workshops and weddings,
- They are located near a large population base with public transport links to facilitate guest attendance, and
- Most importantly, they are interested in promoting the idea of SFSCs in line with the project goals.

The involvement of a journalist (Janine Kennedy, The Irish Farmers Journal - food & lifestyle magazine) in the event proved beneficial, for event promotion and to facilitate interviews during the event. One of the prizes for the winning chef was also an article to highlight their work in the publication. Producers and chefs who were MAP members were given first priority to be involved in the event due to their dedication and efforts already provided to the project.

Table 3: Event organisation timeline

Task	Date	Timing (weeks before/ after the event)
Select and reserve date & venue	Mid-Dec 2022	-10
Confirm availability of Chefs, Producers, Judges & project team	Mid-Dec 2022	-10
Prepare list of available produce and share with chefs	20 th January 2023	-6
Chefs design menu, synchronise and order produce	3 rd February	-4
Event Promotion	Feb 2023	-4 to 0
Ticketing	Feb 2023	-3 to -1
Distributing produce/ingredients to chefs	1 st March 2023	-1
Hosting event	4 th March 2023	0
Collect event photographs, feedback and event reporting	04 th – 10 th March 2023	0 to +1

2.6 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

All agroBRIDGES MAP members from Ireland were invited to the event by email to allow for early booking. Following this the event was promoted via social media (LinkedIn and Twitter), beginning 4 weeks before the event with the initial invitation. After the initial invitation, there was a social media post every 3 to 4 days with information on a different producer or chef to maintain interest in the event and to promote the event team as much as possible. All posts used the same template for consistency of messaging. The event hosts, Airfield Estate shared all posts, as did the journalist that was engaged for the event. Chefs and producers also shared their own posts about the event to promote it to their own customer base / following. This enabled the event promotional material reaching a larger audience.

Figure 5: Pre-event social media post (photo by Janine Kennedy)

Figure 6: Post-event social media post (photo by Janine Kennedy)

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

The event was essentially a very friendly cooking competition between the chefs. Scoring consisted of an aggregate of the scores of three professional judges accounting for 50 %, and the scores of the event attendees, which accounted for the remaining 50 %. A Mentimeter subscription was purchased in order to use the web service to collect and aggregate the attendees’ scores.

Judging Criteria for the Event

- **Ingredients /6 points**
 - Does the dish highlight the use of local and seasonal ingredients?
- **Flavour & Taste /10 points**
 - Do the major ingredients carry the dominant flavours? Do the components fit together? Do the textures reflect the cooking technique?
- **Idea & Creativity /4 points**
 - Do you like the concept behind the dish? Is the idea creative?
- Total score 20

Figure 7: Photos of (a) the event opening and (b) producer interview (Photos by Jennifer Attard and David Barry)

Figure 8: Photos of (a) the winning chef and (b) the second-place dish (Photos by Janine Kennedy)

Figure 9: Photos of two of the producers' stands (Photos by Jennifer Attard)

Figure 10: Event organisers, the winning chef and the interviewer

3.2 Event participation

Table 4: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Organisers	4
Producers	4
Event Attendees	38
Chefs	3
Judges	3
Journalist/Interviewer	1
Total	53

4. Event Validation

Google forms was used to collect feedback from the event. An online QR generator was used to create a QR code that was printed on small pieces of paper and handed out to the attendees at the end of the event. Four days after the event, a reminder with a link to the feedback form was sent by email to all event attendees who agreed to receive emails from organisers. Fifteen responses were collected. The results are summarised in Table 5 below.

4.1.1 Validation of event concept by participants

Table 5: Event validation results

Question	Answers		
Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event?	Yes	No	Not Sure
Attendee answers	12	2	1

Question	Answers					
Did you find this event informative about new/unknown types of food produced in your region?	Very informative	Relatively Informative	Neutral	Not Informative	Not Informative at all	
Attendee answers	8	6	1	0	0	
Did you find this event helpful for getting to know local food businesses, restaurants, their methods and efforts to bring local food closer to you?	Very helpful	Helpful	Neutral	Not very Helpful	Not Helpful at all	
Attendee answers	10	5	0	0	0	
Did you find the activities organised helpful to understand the value of local food, local recipes and their various benefits for your health, the environment, and the society?	Very helpful	Helpful	Neutral	Not very Helpful	Not Helpful at all	
Attendee answers	11	3	1	0	0	
Did you find enough information about how and where to find the local restaurants and kitchens and other hospitality businesses you've met?	Enough and very precise information	Enough information, but I would need more details	Enough information but I need to search further on my own	Not enough information	No information at all	
Attendee answers	7	7	1	0	0	
Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region? How often	Monthly or more often	3-4 times a year	Twice a year	Once a year	Never	I prefer not to answer
Attendee answers	1	6	7	1	0	0

A few comments from the event:

- Chefs and producers who were not from the Dublin area, and were from County Kerry, would like to see an event that is more local to them as they believe it would be highly successful.
- Due to the academic nature of the project partners involved in promoting the event (MTU and Teagasc), a number of attendees were also from academia and therefore were already familiar with SFSC concepts and food sustainability. The stakeholders involved in the event were hopeful however, to have a greater audience from the general public in order for their efforts to increase knowledge around food sustainability. More targeted promotion of the event could have alleviated this issue before selling out tickets to academics.

4.1.2 Validation of “Let’s meet!” guidelines and templates by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event concepts relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

Yes. All event concepts were relevant to the local ecosystems. The chosen concept (culinary event) seemed to be an interesting and topical focus for both the organizers (and key stakeholders) and the participants.

Question #2: Would you organize the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments?

Yes, seasonal nature of Irish produce makes it tricky to organize in Winter. A September/October event would be better to fully realize the opportunity of Irish fresh produce.

Question #3: Did you find the guidelines and templates sufficient for your event organization needs?

Mostly. The participant's sheet was not useful as we needed to collect much more information. We also created a Press Bio template for stakeholders in order to collect their information for social media promotion.

Question #4: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines accurate enough to plan effectively?

Yes.

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Yes. It is clear in the guidelines that they are just an outline, and they serve as a good reminder to ensure that all tasks are completed on time – whether they are followed accurately or not.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

MTU decided to organise the event up in Dublin instead of in their local county (Kerry). This meant that promoting the event and creating worthwhile connections was challenging. It might be more useful to host an event for a more targeted audience / purpose in future.

4.1.4 *Suggestions for improvement of the concept and guidelines*

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

From our experience in organizing the 'Lets meet' event the guidelines were sufficient and allowed enough flexibility to tailor the event to our specific requirements allowing for factors such as venue (location and capacity), promotion material template, labor required and event reporting. The participant's sheet was not beneficial.

5. Conclusions

The overall event is deemed to be successful, with strongly positive feedback from both the involved actors and the attendees. One learning from this event would be to regionalise the event to match the producers with potential customers. This event had a geographic spread of producers from around Ireland, where a range of their produce was used in the food preparation for the event. While this promoted the agroBRIDGES project and the concept of SFSCs and local producers, it did not directly connect new customers to local chefs and producers. A second idea is to have a regional event that is looked at from a fresh / outside perspective by inviting chefs from outside the region to cook with regional produce providing an outside view or fresh perspective of the potential of the produce.